

20IND11 MetHyInfra

Deliverable D2: Technical report on the methods used for the calibration of critical nozzles (CFVNs) as calibration standards under high pressure (at least 90 MPa) operating conditions, and flow rates up to 10 kg/min, with gaseous hydrogen including a comparison of calibration results of nozzles, and determination and validation of uncertainty budgets
DELIVERABLE D2

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This project "Metrology infrastructure for high-pressure gas and liquified hydrogen flows" (MetHyInfra) has received funding from the EMPIR programme co-financed by the Participating States and from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme.

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Summary		
<p>This report was written as part of activity 1.4.3 from the EMPIR Metrology infrastructure for high-pressure gas and liquified hydrogen flows (MetHyInfra) project. It describes the methods used for the calibration of sonic nozzles at inlet pressures up to 62 MPa, and flow rates up to 1.68 kg/min, with gaseous hydrogen. Some observations from attempted flow calibrations are presented, as well as recommended improvements to the experimental setup and procedures.</p>		
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1 Introduction

The overall objective of the MetHyInfra project is to establish a metrological infrastructure which will allow the assessment and calibration of flow meters and sonic nozzles for the measurement of hydrogen flow at high pressures. WP1 aims to develop calibration methods for sonic nozzles and master meters at pressures up to 100 MPa and flow rates up to 10 kg/min. This could provide a needed link between low-pressure (0.5 MPa) and high-pressure calibration behaviour. The targets are linked to hydrogen vehicle applications such as trucks, buses and trains, and to manufacturers of meters or refuelling stations. There are currently no flow testing facilities that can circulate hydrogen at those conditions, so a novel approach was taken in this project.

In Task 1.4, sonic nozzles were installed in a closed-loop hydrogen test facility, in order to perform flow calibrations at pressures up to 62 MPa and flow rates up to 1.68 kg/min. The flow rates and pressures selected were based on the maximum capacity of the test facility. A Coriolis master meter; previously calibrated in Task 1.3; was installed upstream of the nozzles and served as the reference flow device.

This report describes the approach taken for flow calibration of the sonic nozzles. Unfortunately, the calibrations were unsuccessful, but the test installation, protocol and collected data are discussed, as well as recommendations for how the work can be performed successfully in the future.

2 Testing Equipment

2.1 Sonic Nozzle and Holder

A drawing of one of the sonic nozzles to be calibrated is shown in Figure 1. This is based on the ISO 9300 [1] toroidal-throat geometry. The throat diameter is 1 mm. The second nozzle has the same throat diameter but is based on the ISO 9300 cylindrical-throat geometry.

Figure 1: HP nozzle, toroidal, 1 mm throat

Each sonic nozzle was installed in a holder, the design of the holder is shown in Figure 2. The holder was constructed from 316L stainless steel, the design pressure is 100 MPa. The process connections of the holder are 13/16-16UN threads. The holder is disassembled into 2 pieces when installing or removing a nozzle, the connection between the two pieces is an M78x2 union nut. Sealing is achieved with a metal c-ring, these were provided with the holder. Three ports are provided on the nozzle

holder, to accommodate the upstream temperature probe and both upstream and downstream pressure transmitters. The pressure ports use 7/16-20UN female threads, the temperature port is 9/16-18UN.

Figure 2: HP Sonic nozzle holder

2.2 Master Meter

As explained in A1.3.4, Deliverable D1, the selected master meter is a Rheonik RHM04 Coriolis belonging to METAS [2]. The specifications are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Specification of Coriolis Flow Meter and Transmitter

Flow meter type:	RHM 04L GET, SN RHM-22843
Transmitter	RHE 16, SN RHE-22735
Manufacturer:	Rheonik
Flow rate range	(0.2 – 10) kg/h
Pulses/kg	10'000
Connection type:	Autoclave 3/8" MP (9/16-18 UNF female thread)
Maximum pressure rating	1070 bar@50°C

Figure 3 presents the Rheonik Coriolis mass flow meter in its aluminium frame.

Figure 3: Rheonik Coriolis mass flow meter mounted in its frame.

A transmitter is required for power supply to and data transmission from the master meter. The meter, transmitter and cabling are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Flow Meter and Associated Hardware

	<p>Rheonik Coriolis flow meter with cable</p>
	<p>USB cable from transmitter to PC</p>
	<p>Transmitter with connector to CFM (on the back) and connector to the PC (USB-Service)</p>
	<p>Power supply cable for transmitter with adapter</p>
<p>USB data stick with Rheonik flow meter software</p>	

2.3 Test Installation

A modified Maximator test facility was used to circulate hydrogen at the flow rate and pressure ranges required for the sonic nozzle calibration. A schematic of the facility is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Maximator Test Facility

Two compressors were used to circulate the hydrogen in a closed loop, the compressors can operate with very high differential pressures, as required to maintain choked flow through the critical flow nozzles at high inlet pressures. Pressure control is achieved using regulators. A back-pressure regulator maintains the pressure at the compressor outlet, whilst a pressure reducing regulator at the end of the test line sets the compressor inlet pressure. The reference flow device is the master meter described in Section 2.2.

The Coriolis master meter and sonic nozzles were installed near the end of the test line, immediately upstream of the pressure reducing regulator. The presence of two pressure regulators and a sonic nozzle divided the test facility into four zones operating at different pressures. There are several pressure vessels throughout the test facility, which improve pressure and flow stability and allowed the facility to operate at higher flow rates than the compressors alone can provide. Heat exchangers provided temperature control upstream of devices under test and in the return line to compressor. The test facility has its own mass flow meter, whilst it was not planned to be used for reference metering, it was decided to use the process meter output when problems were encountered with the master meter.

Two nozzles were calibrated. Both have a throat diameter of 1 mm, but one has the toroidal-throat geometry according to ISO 9300, and the other has the cylindrical shape. Although they were calibrated individually, both sonic nozzles and holders were installed in parallel. This allowed the number of pressurisation and depressurisation cycles to be minimised.

A drawing of the test installation is shown in Figure 5 and a photo is shown in Figure 6. The flow direction is from left to right. Hydrogen was first introduced to the Coriolis master meter. The flow then split into two parallel branches, one nozzle holder was installed in each branch, and a pair of manual isolation valves were used to isolate the gas flow through either branch.

Figure 5: Drawing of the test installation.

Figure 6: Photo of the test installation.

The test line was installed at the Maximator facility inside a container. This is an ATEX zone, so all instruments used in the test line were ATEX certified for use with hydrogen. The instruments were connected to power supplies and data logging equipment in the non-ATEX area via intrinsically safe barriers.

Measurements were logged and analysed with a laptop equipped with LabVIEW software. Figure 7 shows the LabView user interface.

Figure 7: LabVIEW user interface.

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Figure 8 shows a photo taken during the attempted flow calibrations. The container unit is on the right-hand side. The test line was installed inside this container and the data cables from the flow meter, temperature and pressure sensors were routed outside to the data logging laptop. Due to the limited cable lengths, the laptop and other non-ATEX hardware were used in the outdoor environment, under a mobile shelter.

Figure 8: Installation at Maximator site

Figure 9 shows the view inside the container. The high-pressure gas supply comes from the left. There is a bypass valve which can divert the flow straight to the return line to the compressor. The bypass was fully closed, which meant that all the gas flow was directed through the master meter and sonic nozzles. The test line is not visible on this photo, but it was mounted on the wall directly opposite of the bypass valve, to the right of the door. Some data transmission cables from the test line are visible on the right-hand side of the photo.

Before the bypass valve is a 4-way junction. The line from the bottom port is connected to the pressure relief safety valve. The line from the top port connected to the inlet of the master meter. The tubing from the outlet of the sonic nozzles connected to the return line to the compressor.

Figure 9: View of gas supply and return lines inside the container

Figure 10 shows the test line installed in the container. It was mounted vertically, so the flow direction is from top to bottom.

Figure 10: Test line installed in the container

3 Test Matrix

The calibration points are shown in Table 3. It was planned to allow at least 10 minutes for stabilisation before logging. Each test point would then be logged for a minimum of 2 minutes with at least 2 repeats (3 points total).

The highest flow rate shown in the table was 1.68 kg/min. This was the maximum flow rate that the test facility could supply with the required inlet and differential pressure ranges but falls short of the 10 kg/min target. To provide traceability for up to 10 kg/min target using this approach, it would be necessary to calibrate 6 nozzles and use them in parallel in subsequent applications.

Table 3: Test Matrix

Nozzle Inlet Pressure, MPa	Mass Flow Rate, kg/min	Compressor inlet pressure, MPa	Back-pressure Ratio
62	1.68	50	0.8
50	1.38	36	0.7
25	0.71	10	0.4
15	0.43	3	0.2
10	0.29	1.5	0.2

4 Measurement Procedure

4.1 Installation and leak checking

- Install the master meter and sonic nozzles
- Perform leak test, eliminate leaks as far as possible and estimate leakage rate between master meter and sonic nozzles
- Fill the facility to the required initial pressure
- Zero the master meter

4.2 Flow calibrations

- Open the manual isolation valves up- and downstream of nozzle holder 1
- Close the manual isolation valves up- and downstream of nozzle holder 2
- Start the flow, adjust the compressor speed and pressure regulator settings to achieve 0.29 kg/min. Inlet pressure at the nozzle should 1.5 MPa.
- Wait for stability in flow rate, pressure and temperature. Aim for a consistent pressure and temperature over a two minute period. If either are trending in a consistent direction, the change should be less than 0.1% per minute for pressure or 0.3°C per minute for temperature. It is assumed that it will typically take 10 minutes to reach stability.
- Once conditions are stable, start data logging. Record the flow rate and tube temperature from the master meter and inlet temperature, inlet pressure and outlet pressure for the sonic nozzle. Log for a minimum of 2 minutes.
- Follow the same procedure for repeat points. The points may be carried out in any order
- Once all calibration points are completed for nozzle 1, repeat for nozzle 2. The valve positions for nozzle holders 1 and 2 need to be reversed.

The total time required was estimated at 1.5 days.

5 Results

5.1 Leak checks

After installation, the test line was leak checked by Maximator. This leak check was sufficient to confirm that it was safe to operate the test line with hydrogen. Prior to flow calibrations, further leak checks were carried out to quantify any remaining leaks between the master meter and nozzle holders, and determine the contribution to measurement uncertainty.

In the piping connected to nozzle holder 2, the estimate leak rate was 0.009 g/min, which is 0.003% of the minimum flow rate on the test matrix (0.29 kg/min). In the piping connected to nozzle holder 1, the leakage rate was so low that it could not be accurately measured in a 30 minute interval. The leakage rates were therefore deemed acceptable, and it was decided to proceed with the flow calibrations. The leak rate calculations are shown in the Appendices.

5.2 Flow calibrations

Unfortunately, the flow calibrations were unsuccessful because the master meter failed to provide accurate reference flow rates. This was an unexpected outcome, given that the meter has proven reliable in past projects, including the recent calibration in A1.3.4, Deliverable D1. As of April 2024, the cause is not yet known, but a malfunction with the transmitter unit is suspected. This will be investigated further once the meter and transmitter are returned to METAS.

Despite the failure to perform the calibrations, some data was still recorded under flowing conditions, and it is possible to draw some conclusions which could prove useful to researchers attempting similar studies in the future.

The first observation is on the behaviour of the master meter. The researcher performing the calibrations immediately noticed that the flow rates indicated by the master meter were inaccurate. This is best illustrated using plotted test data. Figure 11 shows the pressure transmitter data for a calibration point. The nozzle inlet pressure (labelled as Keller 1) is 26 MPa and outlet pressure (labelled as Keller 2) is 7.7 MPa, giving a back pressure ratio of 0.3 and estimated flow rate of 0.74 kg/min.

Figure 11: Sonic nozzle pressure measurements for example calibration point

As shown in Figure 12, the flow rate measured by the master meter was clearly incorrect. The flow meter output ranged from -0.06 to +0.06 kg/min. The measured flow rate readings were very small,

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centred around zero and switching between negative and positive, similar trends were observed for other test points.

Figure 12: Master meter measurements for example calibration point

On the other hand, the average flow rate reported by the station flow meter was in agreement with the flow rate estimated from the sonic nozzle pressure measurements. The station flow meter (labelled as “Process meter”) is plotted with the master meter (labelled as “Master meter”) data in Figure 13.

Figure 13: Master meter and process meter comparison at fixed flow rate

Here a second observation is made. Although the process meter provides a realistic average flow rate, the flow rate is not constant and clearly shows the pulsations from the compressor. The frequency of these pulsations is approximately 1 Hz, with flow rates ranging from 0.3 to 1.3 kg/min. These conditions are not desirable for flow calibrations. Even if the master meter was behaving normally, it is unlikely that the calibrations could be performed with the required measurement uncertainty.

More insight is gained on the behaviour of the master meter when monitoring its output as the station operating conditions were being adjusted. The data in Figure 14 shows that the master meter readings are not random, they actually follow a similar trend as the station meter, but the magnitude is wrong. The meter also shows reverse flow at certain times, this is not realistic and instead implies that there may be an offset in the readings.

Figure 14: Master meter and process meter comparison at varying flow rate

The pressure data for this same period is shown in Figure 15. In the period from 17:36 to 17:40, flow rate was constant and choked flow was maintained through the sonic nozzle. The flow rate estimated from the sonic nozzle inlet pressure is roughly 0.92 kg/min, which agrees with the average flow rate reported by the process meter.

Figure 15: Sonic nozzle pressure measurements at varying flow rate

Since the master meter failed to perform, and the measurements from the process meter appeared realistic, it was decided to attempt the flow calibration using the process meter as the reference flow device.

Results from the flow calibrations are shown in Figure 16, compared with the ISO 9300:2022 curves. Unfortunately, the data appears to be unreliable. One notices that the discharge coefficients are much larger than predicted by the ISO 9300 curves. This alone is not a cause for concern, there may be unusual behaviour for hydrogen at high pressure conditions.

There are however other signs that the data is not reliable. First, the discharge coefficients are different for nozzle 1 and nozzle 2. Although these nozzles are based on two different geometries (toroidal and cylindrical), neither the ISO curves nor the previous nitrogen calibrations by METAS and PTB showed such a large difference. Also, the repeatability for each nozzle is poor, shifts of more than 1% are observed in the data for repeat points.

Based on these observations, it is likely that:

- Although the process meter is performing adequately for its intended purpose, it is not measuring with the required uncertainty to act as a reference meter. It is likely over-reading and may need to be calibrated against a suitable reference and zeroed.
- The conditions within the station are not conducive to low uncertainty flow calibrations. Accuracy of the flow meter and/or sonic nozzles are reduced by the pulsating flow.

Figure 16: Calibration results using Maximator process meter as reference

5.3 Loss of containment

On the final day of the measurement campaign, a large leak suddenly appeared. The test facility was shut down and no further flow tests were possible. The source of the leak was found to be the vent hole of the union nut on the holder for nozzle 2, this is shown in Figure 17.

Figure 17: Photo showing location of leaking vent hole on nozzle holder

The most likely cause of the leak is that the union nut came loose during the flow calibrations, but there was insufficient time to disassemble on site and investigate further. The integrity of the nozzle holders will be investigated when they are returned to PTB.

6 Conclusions

The flow calibrations were unsuccessful due to an apparent malfunction with the transmitter of the reference meter. An attempt was made to calibrate the sonic nozzles using the Maximator process meter as a reference. However, this was also unsuccessful. The process meter appears to be over-reading, but more importantly, the repeatability of the measurements was quite poor, with repeat points differing by more than 1%.

In principle, this approach to sonic nozzle calibrations with high-pressure hydrogen may still prove feasible, but the following recommendations are made to researchers attempting similar work in the future:

- Include an additional isolation valve before the master meter, for use in the initial leak checks.
- If possible, improve the flow stability and minimise pulsations. This would most likely require a different test facility to be used, possibly a similar setup with gas accumulators
- If the calibrations must be performed with pulsating flow, preliminary trials should be carried out with the selected master meter and sonic nozzles. The trials could be carried using nitrogen rather than hydrogen, the aim is to understand the influence of pulsating flow, and select equipment which provides the lowest possible measurement uncertainty.

References

[1] International Organisation for Standardization, *ISO 9300:2022 Measurement of gas flow by means of critical flow nozzles*, 2022.

[2] MacDonald, M., de Huu, M., Maury, R., Venslovas, E., & Rasch, M. *Deliverable D1 (A1.3.4) Technical report on the methods used for the calibration of a Coriolis flow meter as a calibration standard under high pressure (at least 90 MPa) operating conditions, and flow rates up to 10 kg/min, with gaseous hydrogen including an uncertainty budget (V1.01)*, 2023. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10075344>

Appendices

Leak rate calculations

Leak rate was determined from temperature and pressure measurements logged over a significant time period, at least 30 minutes. The calculation is as follows:

$$Q_{leak} = \frac{(\rho_2 - \rho_1) \cdot V}{t}$$

Where:

- Q_{leak} = Leak rate, kg/s
- ρ_1 = density of hydrogen in contained in the piping at the start of the logging period, kg/m³
- ρ_2 = density of hydrogen in contained in the piping at the end of the logging period, kg/m³
- V = Estimated piping volume, m³
- t = Logging period, s

Unfortunately, there was no isolation valve near the inlet of the master meter. The leak rate was therefore assessed only for the sections of piping between the needle valves shown (shaded blue sections) below.

Leak rate was not calculated for the piping between the master meter outlet and the first isolation valves. However, the operator sprayed leak detection fluid on all of the relevant joints and confirmed that there were no visual indications of leakage.

Figure 18: Diagram showing the piping sections considered for the leak rate calculation

The following dimensions were used to estimate the relevant piping volume for the leak rate calculation. These are conservative estimates:

Description	Inner diameter m	Length, m	Volume, m ³
Upstream valve to nozzle holder	0.008	0.32	1.61 x 10 ⁻⁵
Nozzle holder	0.016	0.294	5.91 x 10 ⁻⁵
Nozzle holder to downstream valve	0.008	0.1	5.03 x 10 ⁻⁶
Total			8.02 x 10 ⁻⁵

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Plots of variable flow rate

Flow calibrations are normally performed at stable flow rates. However, for the purposes of troubleshooting the master meter, the researchers decided to also log data when flow rates were being adjusted between calibration points.

Figure 19: Measurements taken 16:34 (April 4th)

Figure 20: Measurements taken 17:35 (April 4th)

Figure 21: Measurements taken 18:00 (April 4th)

Figure 22: Measurements taken 18:07 (April 4th)

Figure 23: Measurements taken 18:19 (April 4th)

Plots of stable flow rate

Figure 24: Measurements taken 16:48 (April 4th)

Figure 25: \Measurements taken 17:52 (April 4th)

Figure 26: Measurements taken 18:04 (April 4th)

Figure 27: Measurements taken 18:31 (April 4th)

Figure 28: Measurements taken 12:34 (April 5th)

Figure 29: Measurements taken 12:34 (April 5th)